

THE ROLE OF TEACHER IN TEACHING LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract:

Teacher played very pivotal role in teaching and learning process. In the period covid – 19 pandemic whole education system is turned into digital form. But the importance of teacher is unavoidable. Teachers the construction scaffold of the educational process. Unless and until teaching process cannot go forward without teacher. In ancient period also 'acharya' Guru was teacher. In modern digital world, in 21 centuries the nature of teaching – learning process is changed but the importance of teacher will never have ignored. The teacher is sculpture, mentor, supporter and manger. Nowadays the role of teacher is changing in this pandemic. Teacher is teaching with the help of technology. According to the research findings, the use of technology changes the role of the teachers from a traditional knowledge provide rather into a facilitator guiding and also engaging problem solving with students.

Keywords: *Sculpture, Mentor, Support, Manger*

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Introduction:

Teachers truly are the backbone of society. They are role models to children, offer guidance and dedication and give young people the power of education. Because of teachers, countries are able to further develop socially and economically. Taking on the task of shaping young mind is a big responsibility. To say that teachers can change lives is not an exaggeration. While so much emphasis today is on learning the hard skills necessary to excel in a certain profession. Particular in the postsecondary environment much of the 'life – changing stuff' happens in the younger years as students accumulate knowledge at the hands of good teacher.

Nowadays education used as synonymous of e-learning. Behind the idea of a new digital Era lies a common perception of a profound, expected transformation of our society into a new type of society, usually called the information society. The penetration of new information and communication technologies in all sectors of the economy, in education and everyday life, supposed to bring about this leap into a new digital future. In the period of covid-19 pandemic the whole education system is turned into digital form. The increasing role played by information technology in the development of society calls for an active reaction to the challenges of the information society.

Literature review:

Scottish Govt. (1 October 2010) – Scottish Govt. research and analysis published literature review on teacher education, the role of teacher and professionalism pupil outcomes. The key points of summary mentioned as follows:

It is widely agreed that teaching quality is linked to pupil outcomes and it is often suggested that teacher education contributes to the development of teacher quality. Research shows the teacher quality is significantly and positively

correlated with pupil attainment and that is the most important within school aspect explaining student performance. Furthermore, other studies have found positive relationships between in service teacher training and student achievement (European commission, 2007)

Goe (2007) uses two 'input measures' teacher qualifications and teacher characteristics, a process measure of teacher practices and an outcome measure, teacher effectiveness.

Objectives:

1. To find out the role of teacher in teaching learning process.
2. To find out the various aspects of roles of teacher.
3. To find out the information regarding ancient and modern time period.
4. To find out the impact of technology on roles of teacher.

Scope:

Actually the role of teacher is very border concept but in this paper few roles of teacher has been focused.

Research Methodology:

This paper is based on literature survey.

Role of teacher in ancient period:

In the ancient period, teacher had so many roles for e. g Guru advisor symbol model etc. GU means darkness and RU means to remove. The person who lead the younger generation from darkness to light is known as guru. He is also turn as torch bearer like the light of a torch expels the darkness the teacher with the help of his knowledge removes the darkness of ignorance.

Teachers in ancient period were held in high position in society. Even the kings and rulers respect to them. In that period teacher was considered as a simple also, a symbol of truth, beauty and purity. But in the modern age, it is almost iterated to marry getting a job.

Role of teacher in modern time:

Teachers are best known for the role of education the students that our place in their care. Beyond that, teacher's serve many other roles in the classroom. Teacher set the tone of their classrooms, build a warm environment, mentor and nurture students, become role models and listen the look for signs of trouble.

The teacher has so many roles are there we have listed very few of them which are as follows:

The sculpture:

The sculptor text full responsibility for the presentation of all relevant and material. He controls the schedule and the curriculum and controls the work of the students. She devotes the sometime to help the weakest of the students, because this is a part of this task. The dialogue in the classroom aims mainly at clarifying the presentation of the textbook and correcting student works. I am correcting students work s.

Mentor:

One of the biggest roles a teacher may have is that of a mentor. Students look up to teachers and many pattern their own behaviour and work it ethic to match the instructor. An older teacher can even be a mentor to a younger teacher who is just starting out in the profession.

Support:

A teacher must act as the support person when the student needs this help. Support can come in many form such as a

coach, gender and even a counsellor. In professional circles a teacher may even have to support other teachers landing a particular subject matter.

The manager:

The manager looks at the classroom as a working place, and his task is to manage the joint efforts effectively towards the best possible result. Everybody should know how to learn, and she delegates tasks and responsibilities. She also varies working methods. she is aware of individual differences and uses much time in explaining what to do and why. She is a democratic leader and discuss and strategies with her students, but she also knows that structure and management is necessary.

Impact of technology on the roles of teachers:

According to the research findings, the use of technology changes the role of the teacher from a traditional knowledge provider rather into a facilitator guiding the students learning processes and engaging in joint problem solving with students.

Technology use allows many more students to be actively thinking about information, making choices and executing skills a is typical in teacher led lessons. However, tool uses of technology are highly compatible with this new teacher role, since they stimulate so much active mental work on the part of students.

Technology will not be able to avoid the onset of a pandemic; never the less it can assist in managing a crisis more effectively.

We all know how badly covid-19 has impacted our lives, both personal and professional. During this time of sheer uncertainty and constant fear, our willingness to adopt technology has been our lifeline.

In brief we wanted to look at some of fundamental aspects of teaching and some of the new challenges we already are facing with the technologies available. We are convinced that both the organisation and the strategies of teaching and learning in education will have to change in digital era. But they will have to change through exploration and reflection on you practices within the education and not through speeches from outside.

The future of education does not really solely on new and innovative tech and in YouTube take tools, but on creating safe and accessible learning equal for all.

Conclusion:

In brief, the teacher's role is to help students learn by imparting knowledge to them and by setting up a situation in which students can and will learn effectively. But teachers fill a complex set of roles, which vary from one society to another and from one educational level to another. So, the role of teacher is changing day by day.g

References:

<https://ceoworld.biz/ceoinsider/>

<https://online.purdue.edu/blog/education/how-has-technology-changed-education>

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

<https://www.researchgate.net/>